

Case Report

Live Fish: unique foreign body throat

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Abstract: Accidental ingestion of live fish is a very rare condition. Here we are reporting a very uncommon condition, a rare case of live fish stuck in throat of a fisherman and its twitching lead to fatal respiratory distress. The fish was removed in Toto under local anesthesia and patient's life was saved.

Key words: Live fish, Throat, Respiratory distress.

Introduction:

Cases of foreign bodies in Ear, Nose and Throat have been reported since ages and probably they are the most common emergencies. Swallowing of foreign bodies by children, old age people and mentally deranged patients is an occurrence of considerable frequency¹. Here we are reporting a rare case of live fish stuck in throat of a fisherman and its twitching lead to fatal respiratory distress.

Case report:

A 40 year old fisherman was brought to the Emergency Room with a live fish stuck in throat. He had severe pain in throat with drooling of blood tinged saliva and difficulty in breathing. He was unable to talk. His relatives told that a fish stuck in his throat. Patient's throat was examined and indirect laryngoscopy was done which showed pooling of saliva only with little blood, moreover the patient was not very cooperative. As we were not very much convinced by the history, so an immediate X-ray soft tissue neck was done and patient was taken to Operation Theater without waiting for X-ray film. The picture of neck seen on X-ray was difficult to believe. There was marked prevertebral widening which was completely obliterating the air shadow of trachea. An intense observation revealed a fish like shadow in the throat (Fig.I). Under local anesthesia a Direct Laryngoscope was introduced. After suctioning the saliva in throat the tail of the fish came in picture. The fish was badly stuck in throat, moreover local edema and mucosal swelling tightened it up there so pulling the fish became difficult. With the help of forceps a maneuver was done to bring the fish in streamlined position in throat and with little jerky and rhythmic movements the fish was delivered in Toto (Fig II). As soon as the fish was removed the patient got relief on the Operating table itself. A Ryle's tube was then passed. The detailed history from the patient revealed that on the day of incidence, he was fishing in the nearby Gorai creek and happened to net two fishes each about five inches long. He was trying to retrieve them from net. He removed one fish from net, held it with his teeth and then tried to remove the other one from net. This was the time when the one with in his mouth started twitching and slid into his throat, got stuck up there. The

fisherman choked and became breathless. He then tried to remove this twitching fish by putting his finger in his throat which worsened his condition as this effort resulted in further swelling in throat with bleeding.

Fig I

Fig II

Discussion:

The list of varied types of foreign bodies removed from human body is getting bigger and bigger. Coin, poorly chewed food, safety pins, bones and toy parts are common foreign bodies², but can be a Glass ball³, a working wristwatch⁴, a live shell, or something we can't imagine. As in this case also the introduction of finger to get rid of foreign body caused local injury and edema, moreover the bloody secretions drooling from mouth of the patient raised the anxiety and had a negative psychological pressure with impending doom, which further worsen the condition.

References:

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News Letter

1. **Dr. Orjeta Tonuzi**, Consultant E.N.T. Surgeon from Tirana Albania is joining one month observership in Department of E.N.T. at M.P.Shah Medical College Jamnagar under Dr. Vikas Sinha, Dean Professor E.N.T. and Dr. Viral A.Chhaya Professor and Head E.N.T.
2. **Dr. Viral A. Chhaya**, Professor and Head E.N.T., M.P.Shah Medical College Jamnagar delivered lecture on "Thyroplasty" at Medical College Ujjain (M.P.)
3. **Dr. Vikas Sinha**, Dean, Professor E.N.T., M.P.Shah Medical College Jamnagar performed live Rhinoplasty surgery and endoscopic D.C.R. surgery at Medical College, Kathmandu, Nepal
4. **Dr. Rajesh Vishwakarma**, professor and Head E.N.T., B.J.Medical College Ahmadabad attended
 - (a) Pediatric audiology conference at Denmark
 - (b) Cochlear implant conference at Sweden
 - (c) Organised Otology workshop at Ahmedabad with department of E.N.T. B.J.Medical College Ahmedabad and A.O.I. Ahmedabad branch and demonstrated live cochlear implant surgery. The other faculty were Dr. Ravi Ramalingam Chennai and Dr. S.K.Bhansali Ahmedabad
5. **Dr. Girish Mishra**, Professor and Head E.N.T. Pramukhswami Medical College Karamsad, Anand delivered lecture
 - (a) Cochlear implant at I.M.A. Baroda
 - (b) Thyroid gland – Surgeons perspective at Baroda
 - (c) Organized workshop on "Tobacco ceasession clinic" at Pramukhswami Medical College, Anand
6. **Dr. Ranjan Aiyer** Professor and Head E.N.T. Govt. Medical College Baroda was judge at All India Rhinology Conference Udaipur for junior consultant award paper
7. **Dr. Farida Wadia** Surat delivered lecture
 - (a) Congenital deafness and middle ear at Pediatric Association Surat
 - (b) Endoscopic and skull base surgery- newer advance at Physician and pediatric Association Valsad
 - (c) Panel discussion on Frontal Sinus at All India Rhinology Conference Udaipur
8. **Dr. Ajay Shah**, Associate Professor E.N.T. N.H.L. Medical College Ahmedabad
 - (a) delivered lecture on "Treatment of Laryngotracheal Stenosis by Laser" at Rajkot E.N.T. Association
 - (b) Panelist on "Sinuses and beyond" at Ahmedabad
9. **Dr. Jawahar Talsaniya**, Associate Professor E.N.T. N.H.L. Medical College Ahmedabad
 - (a) delivered lecture on "Allergic Rhino sinusitis" at general practitioner Ahmedabad
 - (b) Elected as governing body member at all India Rhinology Society
 - (c) Participated in panel discussion on "Allergic Polyposis" at Ahmedabad E.N.T. Association
10. **Dr. Keyur Mehta**, Assistant Professor E.N.T. Govt. Medical College Bhavnagar was given "Best Temporal Bone Dissector Award" at Temporal Bone Dissection workshop at Nanavati hospital Mumbai
11. **Dr. Hiten Maniyar** joined as Assistant Professor E.N.T. at M.P.Shah Medical College, Jamnagar
12. **Dr. Rahul Patel** joined as Assistant Professor E.N.T. at Govt. Medical College, Surat
13. **Dr. Rahul Gupta** joined as Assistant Professor E.N.T. at Govt. Medical College, Baroda

